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Transitioning an engineering classroom from traditional lectures to a partially-flipped format

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ABSTRACT

Traditional university teaching methods are grounded in the delivery of content via passive, didactic lectures that are largely seen as an efficient but not necessarily effective means of mass information transfer. Higher-order, deeper-thinking activities and the application of concepts are reserved for the domain of small classes such as tutorials.

The “flipped-classroom” approach shifts the role of the lecture away from basic knowledge transfer to a facilitated, more participatory problem-solving environment. Basic knowledge is transferred via creation of online learning modules utilising short, focused videos. Moving lectures to such a mode of delivery shifts the onus of learning basic material to students, allowing them a level of independence to take ownership of their own learning. Teacher-student interaction in lectures is potentially increased under such a situation and provides ample opportunities for active learning activities.

This paper presents a structured approach to transitioning a third-year engineering subject with 150 students from a traditional lecture format to a partially-flipped classroom, adapting research-based templates from the five phase ADDIE model - Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. The first four phases are described in detail as applied to the subject, including analyses of the subject and learning environment, design and development of learning materials, and implementation of the platform for delivery of video lectures and feedback. The final phase refers to the experimental set up and evaluation of results, where the authors assessed resource-effectiveness and measured students’ confidence, engagement, satisfaction and video preferences in order to determine the efficacy of their approach.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Higher Education is currently undergoing wide-spread transformational change driven by innovative technologies and concepts that fuse personalised, collaborative, open, interactive, and visualised learning. The educational transformation is underscored by overall digitalisation trends which have profoundly affected the way people interact with, have access to and use digital information for learning. Such universal shifts have forced changes in traditional methods of delivery of content and the educational environment itself. Specifically, substitution of traditional, didactic lectures by online digital videos has led to decreased lecturing time [1,2], enabling an increase in scalability in terms of the number of students that can be accommodated and allowing flexibility in terms of their study schedule. Video lectures can be made available for an unlimited number of students and activities can be arranged more often and with smaller groups of students, which increases the potential for teacher-student interaction. In addition, teaching time can be reduced, specifically time devoted to simple repetition of the same content from one year to another whereas repetitive instruction in the video should be avoided [3].

The Australian education system has readily embraced the new technology and incorporated digital resources into students' education from an early age. The flow-on effects of this are now being seen at the University level, with students inherently possessing a familiarity with accessing and digesting such information, becoming so-called "digital natives". Despite the fact that fully online courses are not wholly accredited in the higher education system in Australia, innovative course designs and educational technologies range from very basic integration of digital tools to complete transformations of the teaching approach. Although the level of implementation can vary in different universities, the critical question teachers face is the same: are these course design approaches effective in terms of improving students' learning experiences? In considering this question, teachers must also attempt to evaluate in advance if such course design can be realistically implemented, which teaching and technological support is needed and if it is resource-effective and scalable in the long term.

The "flipped classroom" concept has recently emerged as a methodology that encompasses multiple different modern education strategies [4]. The flipped, or "inverted", classroom definition ranges from basic to more advanced versions. The originators of the approach, Bergmann and Sams, distinguish for the flipped classroom what has been traditionally done before class, in class and after class at home [5]. The definition that is used by the authors of this paper is that the flipped classroom refers to preparation with digital materials before class and activities in the class [6]. The structure of the flipped classroom is therefore in this case a combination of two components: passive lectures and active in-class work. The passive lecture component is typically delivered as a series of short video lectures that focus on basic information transfer and are placed online before the class. The in-class time is then devoted to activities that facilitate a more participatory problem-solving environment, helping students assimilate material and better develop complex skills.

Despite evidence of learning advantages from inverting the classroom in such a manner, teachers mention a substantial list of barriers and recommendations for flipped classroom design improvement [7]. The primary barrier identified is the significant investment in time and cost by the teacher to create the resources to support the flipped classes, without a clear idea of the sorts of savings such an

investment will provide in the longer term. Furthermore, there are no clear guidelines or support systems that a potential implementer can adopt to measure the learning outcomes to his/her standards, which is crucial specifically for inexperienced teachers.

In this paper, a structured flipped classroom design approach is presented in the context of an Electrical Engineering subject for third-year Bachelor students at a large university in Australia. The approach taken was to use an adapted ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation) model [8] in the flipped classroom design, the “Flipped Classroom Design Approach” (FCDA). The FCDA utilises a guided template for redesign which was partly filled before the start of content development for the new version of the subject and is covered in detail in Section 2 of this paper. A detailed resource-effectiveness analysis is performed in Section 3 using classical investment modelling [9], which assesses the economic viability of the designed flipped classroom. This analysis quantifies how the flipped classroom implementation, and specifically video production, utilises existing resources.

2 FLIPPED CLASSROOM COURSE DESIGN APPROACH

In order to transition the subject to a more interactive and innovative learning experience, the “Flipped Classroom Design Approach” (FCDA) was used, considering the preference of the lecturer to employ a Video-based Learning (VBL) approach. Overall, the FCDA template includes 3 stages (plus an initial “reason to flip” stage) which reflects the ADDIE model and is shown in *Fig. 1*. The design approach taken was the result of a scoping review based on 100 most cited papers on flipped classrooms and practical experiments, available online together with an online course [10] and implemented in a number of other courses in Lappeenranta University of Technology (LUT) and universities of the CEPHEI consortium. VBL embedded into the flipped classroom concept empowers potential in resource savings despite its initial costs. Together with an appropriate design approach it can become a sustainable and economically viable way of delivering content for a subject.

Fig. 1. FCDA template stages

2.1 Stage 0: Reasons to flip the classroom

In addition to the wide-range of published evidence of improvements in learning outcomes from switching to a more active teaching environment utilising flipped classrooms [4], The University of Melbourne recently made a number of recommendations about strategic directions to pursue in the areas of curriculum structure and development, teaching, learning and assessment approaches. In particular, Recommendations 1-3 of the Flexible Academic Programming project focused on the role of lectures as the dominant teaching delivery method at the university and the need to rethink their number, format and content. With the evidence showing a decline in students' attendance at lectures over a typical semester, it was clear that the current lecture environment, while being a less-than-ideal learning environment, is also not conducive to student engagement and may further be an inhibitor to building a sense of cohort. With this in mind, it was decided to transition a third-year engineering subject from a traditional lecture format to a partially-flipped classroom.

2.2 Stage 1: Analysis (Context and Resources)

The subject that underwent the flipped classroom transformation is a third-year, Bachelor's level subject with an enrolment of 150 students. The subject develops a fundamental understanding of the concepts behind and tools used for the analysis and design of analog and digital electronic systems and is administered by the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering. It is also a core requirement for those majoring in Mechatronic Systems. A traditional teaching method was previously employed, consisting of 36 hours (3 x 1 hour lectures a week for 12 weeks) of lectures focusing on basic knowledge transfer with some worked examples and 24 hours (1 x 2 hours a week for 12 weeks) or practical workshop classes. The expected total time commitment for such a subject is 170 hours over the semester and is inclusive of all contact time and private study. Students enrolled in the subject are in their third year of study, however they have unlikely had any exposure to a flipped classroom in their undergraduate studies to date. It was not seen as necessary to alter the intended learning objectives for the subject.

The learning environment is a typical 200 seat lecture theatre for lectures and a laboratory seating 32 students for the practical workshop classes. Students typically work in groups of 2 or 3 on practical or tutorial-style problems in these classes and are guided by two teaching assistants. Due to timetabling constraints it was not possible to change any of the venues for the redeveloped iteration of the subject.

2.3 Stage 1: Resource-effectiveness model

The *Resource-effectiveness* model acknowledges economic viability of the flipped classroom implementation. To assess its resource-effectiveness, the costs required for its design, development and implementation are estimated together with the possible pay off period. Economic viability was assessed via classical investment modelling, known also as *capital budgeting analysis* [9]. Investment modelling estimates future cash flows generated by an investment and uses Net Present Value (NPV), which shows total project value, Internal Rate of Return (IRR), which describes the discount rate at which NPV would be zero and Discounted Payback Period (DPP), which shows a period of time after which the investment pays off [11].

The approach was adapted from the resource-effectiveness analysis for a flipped classroom implementation [12], which reveals a pay-off period from 3 to 6 years depending on two different video creation cases and was taken as a basis to set the input data for the current study. The specifications of the input data are presented in *Fig. 2*. The parameter values were acquired by observations and interviews with the lecturer of the subject.

Parameter	Description
Professors time	Preparation + Recording (planning, discussing via meetings)+Integration in the course
PhD Student time	Preparation + Recording + Editing+ Integration
Video duration (of pure video)	Duration of the resulting video material
Compressibility rate	The rate of corresponding lecturing time to the time of the video material substituting it
Repetition rate	The number of times the video material is used per year
Infrastructure costs	The costs of required supporting equipment and software
Professors salary	Official registered salary of the participated professor
Assistant salary	Official registered salary of the participated assistant

Fig 2. Specifications of input data to determine cost-effectiveness

2.4 Stage 2: Realisation (Design and Development)

The preparation for the subject redesign commenced in September 2018, with the subject beginning in March 2019. Taking into account available resources and time commitments, it was decided to make a partial transition of the large 150-student classroom into a video-based flipped classroom form.

Videos were planned to be the main component of the course redesign - 20 short video episodes were produced, reflecting 17 topics. They were recorded over one month in the School of Engineering’s professional studio at The University of Melbourne. The video recording space is equipped with a professional camera, lighting, green screen and audio-support equipment. Following recording, videos were edited in software in collaboration with a PhD student over the next 4 months using Final Cut Pro X. The general design of the video constituted an introduction and conclusion graphic of around 7 seconds each, shown in *Fig. 3*. The introduction and conclusion included the university name, subject number and name, while the conclusion also included LUT as a collaborator. The main body of the video had a white background (substitution for green screen) and approximately 1-2 minutes long discrete clips smoothly merged together, where each reflects one slide, respectively. Each video required approximately 5 hours for its development, with editing constituting the majority of the PhD student’s time, whereas preparation, recording and integration took approximately 20% percent of the total development time.

Fig 3. Screenshots from the designed videos (lecturer intentionally pixelated)

According to a number of research studies, the optimal video length varies from 3 to 20 minutes, with most finding it to be in the 10–15 minute range [2,4,13]. In this case, each recorded video approximately reproduced the information content of one traditional 45-minute lecture and ranged in duration between 06:21 and 14:59 minutes with the average being 9 minutes. In total, 3.5 hours of video was recorded. The *Compressibility Rate* of video lectures was identified as ranging between 3–7 and a value of 3 was used in the cost-effectiveness analysis as the worst-case scenario.

Migrating the basic information transfer of the theory to the online videos in the flipped classroom design allowed the lectures to be reformatted to a more interactive nature. It was deemed that a 30% reduction in the necessary lecturing could be achieved - from 36 hours of lectures in the traditional form to 24 interactive lectures as shown in Fig. 4. The remaining twelve hours of traditional lecture time, which had already been timetabled, were transformed into optional unstructured discussion sessions and maintained the total contact time for the subject. These sessions essentially became the consultation time for the subject that would normally be held by the lecturer at other times. All other time commitments in the subject remained unchanged.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the traditional and flipped class structures

2.5 Stage 3: Implementation and Evaluation

The course implementation and evaluation methods were planned in advance in a general form. It was decided that videos would be hosted on YouTube and embedded to the open source platform EdPuzzle, which lets instructors add questions and comments in the videos. It was planned that the videos would be integrated and open for the students one week before the topic so that students have time to view them before the class. The questions in the videos were aimed to test students' understanding of the concepts and in some videos instruments of measuring their confidence in solving a particular problem were integrated. For example, students

were posed an example problem at the beginning of the video, asked how confident they are to solve it, shown the video and then asked again on their confidence to solve it. The videos were also divided according to ones which the students were required to watch without skipping sections and ones which they could skip. EdPuzzle data analytics can reveal the detailed video-watching behaviour of the students, including how they watch or do not watch each chunk of the video. In addition, it was planned to evaluate students' skills in the class, their overall satisfaction with and preferences for different types of videos. There were no changes in grading for the subject.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Resource-Effectiveness

One of the indicators of resource usage for video development is the *development ratio*, which is the proportion of time spent for video recording to the video duration. The higher the development ratio, the higher the associated costs for video recording and editing [12]. In our resource-effectiveness analysis we consider one case of video production under two scenarios of *repetition rate* in future years as shown in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Flipped classroom viability analysis under two scenarios

Parameter	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
Repetition rate	1	4
Compressibility rate	3	3
Inputs		
Total video duration, hours	3.5	
Professor time (recording), hours	22	
PhD student time (recording and editing), hours	107	
Costs		
PhD student work-related costs, Euro	1834	
Professor's work-related costs, Euro	880	
Total investment (excluding infrastructure costs), Euro	2714	
Revenues		
Saved lecture time, hours per year	10.5	42
Savings, Euro per year	420	1680
Results		
Development ratio	36.85	
Net present value (NPV), Euro	1684	14878
Internal rate of return (IRR)	13%	162%
Discounted payback period (DPP), years	6.6	1.6

Scenario 1 describes the conditions where the videos will be elaborated once a year and scenario 2 where the videos will be elaborated four times a year. Under both scenarios, video elaboration is profitable: NPV is above zero, IRR is substantially higher than the discount rate used (1%), and DPP is 6.6 years and 1.6 years respectively. Principally, the flipped classroom viability analysis justifies the economic viability of flipping lectures with video material, in addition to the obvious educational benefits of providing a more active learning environment.

A development ratio equal to 36-minutes per minute of video corresponds well with observed rates in practice of other universities [12] and means that employing the videos only once a year is enough to pay off the initial costs within 7 years. With increased experience in production of video material, and/or a reduction in the complexity of the videos, an even more favourable development ratio could be achieved, which would make the flipped classroom even more economically attractive.

4 DISCUSSION

A number of observations were made from the video development component of the flipped classroom

- Video editing specifically is a very time-consuming approach and the type of video being produced should be selected wisely. The initial time estimations of producing the videos can increase by 1.2–2 times during the process, depending on the complexity of editing required.
- Video integration in the chosen online platform requires specifically designated time and good planning.
- Errors in the videos can attract special attention and could be more damaging to student learning than mistakes in the class, which can be easily corrected.
- The timing of the release of online videos is crucial to ensure students are prepared for the in-class sessions.

Due to constraints and long lead-times in the university subject approval process, it was not possible to alter the assessment components of the subject. It is planned to introduce an assessment component to encourage more student engagement in the lectures and reward the prior watching of the online videos. Also, teaching venues could be selected in the future to be more conducive to the new format of the active-learning lectures.

The evaluation component of the flipped classroom implementation, in terms of student surveys, feedback and academic results is only partially available at the time of writing and will be the subject of a follow-up publication. Preliminary results indicate that despite some initial issues with understanding the flipped classroom format and timed release of the video lectures, the students have readily engaged with the concept and have had improved confidence when tackling problems.

5 CONCLUSION

Adopting the structured “Flipped Classroom Design Approach”, based on the ADDIE model, to a third-year undergraduate engineering subject produced a flipped classroom that supported an increase in the number and breadth of in class active-learning opportunities. In addition to the known pedagogical benefits of moving to a flipped classroom model, this study used a profitability analysis to put to rest one of

the major concerns of teachers when it comes to migrating to a flipped classroom model by justifying the economic viability of flipping the lectures with video material. If the videos produced are utilised more often, the economic viability of the approach is even more pronounced and demonstrates its tolerance to influential factors suggesting notable flexibility in video elaboration.

Given that it was an initial deployment of the flipped classroom, the lessons learned employing the structured FCDA under the ADDIE model could speed up the process for transforming other subjects in the future. The remaining part of the evaluation, using student survey data and measuring the effects on the flipped classroom on student engagement and academic results will be disseminated when they become available.

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